

EBFMC25-OP-81 · Diagnosis and Treatment Rates of Chronic Hepatitis C in Anti-HCV Positive Patients in Ordu

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AUTHORS

Hatun Ozturk Cerik
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0277-5443>

Ugurcan Cetiner
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-4314-3722>

Celali Kurt
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4419-4508>

Arzu Altuncekic Yildirim
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1141-9838>

Rana Soydemir
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3669-6879>

Fatma Ozdemir Tas
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9573-3667>

Asuman Akbas Demiroglu
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4880-7828>

AFFILIATIONS

Department of Infectious Diseases
Ordu University
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: According to the World Health Organization's (WHO) Global Hepatitis Report 2024, approximately 50 million people worldwide are living with hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection. In 2022 alone, nearly 1 million new HCV infections were projected, with about 1% of the global population expected to suffer from chronic HCV infection. In Turkey, the prevalence of HCV infection ranges between 0.3% and 3.1%. The development of direct-acting antiviral (DAA) drugs has revolutionized treatment, making Chronic Hepatitis C (CHC) curable in up to 95% of cases. Consequently, a disease that was once fatal has become curable for individuals who have access to treatment. The WHO aims to reduce new hepatitis infections by 80% and hepatitis-related deaths by 65%, and to increase the diagnosis and treatment rate to 90% by 2030.

Materials and Methods: This study aimed to determine the rate of HCV-RNA (PCR) testing among patients with positive anti-HCV results in Ordu province between January 1, 2021, and December 31, 2024. Additionally, the study assessed the treatment rate among patients with confirmed CHC and the cure rate in those who received therapy. Data were collected from all healthcare centers in Ordu during the specified period.

Results: A total of 2,695 positive anti-HCV test results were identified. Of these, 784 (29%) were repeat tests, leaving 1,911 unique anti-HCV positive patients. Among these patients, 1,038 (54.3%) were female. Only 873 patients (45.6%) underwent further testing with HCV-RNA PCR, while 1,038 (54.3%) did not. Of the tested

patients, 60 were found to be HCV-RNA positive and were diagnosed with CHC. Of those, 59 (98.3%) received treatment with DAA therapy. The sustained virologic response (SVR) rate among treated patients was 100%.

Conclusion: DAA therapies have significantly altered the clinical course of chronic hepatitis C, transforming it into a manageable and curable disease for those who receive treatment. However, this study revealed that more than half of the patients with anti-HCV positivity did not undergo confirmatory HCV-RNA testing. Among those who did and received treatment, the cure rate reached 100%. These findings emphasize the importance of improving access to diagnostic and treatment services to reach global elimination targets.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

HCV, hepatitis C, direct-acting antivirals

INTRODUCTION

According to the 2024 Global Hepatitis Report by the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 50 million people worldwide are living with hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection. In 2022, about one million new HCV infections were reported, and it is estimated that roughly 1% of the global population suffers from chronic HCV infection (Assoumou et al., 2020). The distribution of HCV is uneven globally, with the European and Eastern Mediterranean regions being more heavily affected. However, there are notable differences in HCV prevalence between countries. In Turkey, the prevalence of HCV infection ranges from 0.3% to 3.1% (Feld & Ward, 2021; Kose et al., 2014; Lazarus et al., 2018; Ozer et al., 2012). Chronic HCV infection (CHC) can lead to cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, and death. Fortunately, the recent introduction of direct-acting antiviral (DAA) medications has made it possible to cure CHC in up to 95% of cases. To eliminate hepatitis, the WHO set goals for the 2016–2030 period to reduce new hepatitis infections by 80% and hepatitis-related deaths by 65%, while increasing diagnosis and treatment rates to 90% (Safreed-Harmon et al., 2019). However, achieving elimination requires identifying infected individuals and initiating their treatment. Despite the availability of effective treatment, HCV remains underdiagnosed and undertreated, with significant gaps in the care cascade. According to WHO's 2024 report, between 2015 and 2022, only 36% of people living with hepatitis C were diagnosed, and only 20% received curative treatment. By the end of 2022, approximately 12.5 million people had received treatment, which is far below the target required to meet the 2030 elimination goals (Assoumou et al., 2020).

Closing the gaps between diagnosis and treatment is therefore essential for HCV elimination. The WHO has emphasized the importance of micro-elimination strategies - defined as elimination within a specific population. The rationale behind this approach is that elimination on a smaller scale is more tangible and realistic and can serve as a pilot model for national programs aiming for macro-elimination (Thomas et al., 1994). Micro-elimination is less intimidating, complex, and costly than nationwide efforts, making it a feasible strategy.

In Turkey, until recently, CHC treatment was reimbursed only in tertiary care hospitals, according to the Healthcare Implementation Communiqué (SUT). In Ordu province, CHC patients are treated solely at Ordu University Training and Research Hospital. Patients identified as anti-HCV positive at primary healthcare centers must be referred to Infectious Diseases or Gastroenterology clinics for HCV PCR confirmation. However, a lack of awareness among other specialties regarding the curability of CHC, or oversight of anti-HCV positive test results, may delay treatment. Such delays can result in fibrosis progression, cirrhosis, or hepatocellular carcinoma.

In this study, we aimed to determine the referral rate of anti-HCV positive patients to the only tertiary hospital in Ordu, the rate of HCV PCR testing among these patients, and the treatment rate among those with confirmed HCV PCR positivity. Additionally, we sought to evaluate sustained virologic response (SVR) rates among treated patients and assess the correlation between anti-HCV titers and HCV PCR results to estimate a basal titer threshold that may help identify false positives. If we find that many patients were not referred or treated, we plan to establish an alert system via the hospital information system and provide training and awareness

initiatives across district hospitals and family health centers in Ordu to support micro-elimination and reach WHO targets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a non-interventional, observational, cross-sectional, retrospective study encompassing data from all hospitals in Ordu capable of performing anti-HCV testing. Ethics approval was obtained from the Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Ordu University. During the study period, HCV PCR testing was available exclusively at the molecular microbiology laboratory of Ordu University Training and Research Hospital. CHC treatment was likewise only available at the Infectious Diseases Department of the same institution. Therefore, all anti-HCV positive patients in Ordu were expected to be referred to this hospital for testing and treatment. Primary data sources included the laboratory databases of the Ordu Provincial Health Directorate and Ordu University Training and Research Hospital. Lists of anti-HCV positive patients and those who underwent HCV PCR testing were compared. Treatment information was obtained from patient records.

The study included all patients who tested anti-HCV positive between January 1, 2021, and December 31, 2024. Collected variables included demographics (e.g., gender, residence), laboratory results (anti-HCV and HCV RNA), time from positive anti-HCV result to treatment initiation (if any), the specialty of the physician ordering the HCV RNA test, and treatment responses. The proportion of anti-HCV positive patients who received HCV PCR testing and the treatment rate among HCV RNA positive individuals were calculated.

Data were analyzed primarily using descriptive statistics. Normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. For non-normally distributed variables, medians and interquartile ranges (IQRs) were reported. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare non-normally distributed quantitative variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS V23.

RESULTS

Between January 1, 2021, and December 31, 2024, a total of 2695 anti-HCV positive test results were recorded in Ordu. After excluding 784 duplicate tests from the same patients, the number of unique anti-HCV positive patients was 1911. Of these patients, 1038(54.3%) were female. It was determined that only 873 (45.6%) of the anti-HCV positive patients were tested for HCV-RNA, while 1038 (54.3%) patients were not tested for HCV-RNA. Among the patients who were tested for HCV-RNA, 60 patients were positive and diagnosed with CHC. Of the patients diagnosed with CHC, 59 (98.3%) were treated with DAE drugs, and the sustained viral response rate was 100% among the treated patients (Figure 1).

DISCUSSION

Prior to 2015, CHC was a challenging infection to treat, with limited efficacy and the risk of progression to end-stage liver disease. With the advent of DAAs, CHC has become a curable condition with high SVR rates (Thomas et al., 1994). The accessibility of these treatments has brought Turkey closer to achieving WHO's 2030 elimination goals.

Despite the efficacy of DAAs, patient attrition occurs at multiple points in the HCV care cascade. Lack of awareness regarding CHC curability, failure to investigate anti-HCV positive results, and inadequate referral to treatment are major barriers. In our study, only 45.6% of anti-HCV positive patients underwent HCV PCR testing. Similarly, U.S.-based studies have shown that 72% of anti-HCV positive individuals were tested for HCV RNA (World Health Organization, 2017; World Health Organization, 2022), while others reported that only 7–18% received confirmatory testing.

Among those tested in our study, 98.3% of patients (59/60) with a positive HCV RNA test were referred for treatment. Sustained viral responses were achieved in all patients receiving treatment. Increasing testing, improving linkage to care, and ensuring universal access to treatment are key strategies for achieving elimination. WHO's cascade of care includes four milestones: infected, diagnosed, treated, and cured (Yildirim et al., 2014). A consensus group of experts from Europe, Australia, and North America has expanded this into seven steps, including disease staging and post-SVR follow-up (Zucker et al., 2018). Countries are advised to analyze their cascade data, identify gaps, and strengthen inter-stage connections (Assoumou et al., 2020).

Our data indicate that the proportions of diagnosed, treated, and cured patients in Ordu fall short of elimination targets. A nationwide study screening 1,000 anti-HCV positive patients found that 78.5% underwent HCV PCR testing, of whom 54% were HCV RNA positive; among those, 72.8% received treatment. The study also showed that non-surgical specialties ordered HCV PCR more frequently than surgical ones. The lack of HCV RNA testing among many anti-HCV positive patients leaves a substantial portion of the infected population untreated, representing a major obstacle to elimination.

CONCLUSION

Although CHC is a curable and manageable infection, lack of awareness and inadequate referral hinder elimination efforts. Underdiagnosis remains a critical barrier. For successful micro-elimination, strategies such as awareness campaigns, educational initiatives, integration of alert systems into health information networks, and improving test-to-treatment linkage must be implemented.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Hatun Ozturk Cerik

Department of Infectious Diseases

Ordu University

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0277-5443>

hatunozturkcerik@gmail.com